

Effect of rice stubble on stem borer hibernation

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Stem borers (SB) (*Scirpophaga* and *Sesamia* spp.) are serious rice pests in Pakistan. They hibernate in the stubble of harvested fields. The Agriculture Department recommends that stubble be destroyed soon after harvest. However, most farmers either don't till fields to destroy stubble, or else plant another crop such as wheat or shaftal (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) without thorough cultivation. Therefore, enough stubble remains for SB hibernation.

We assessed the level of SB hibernation in stubble from uncultivated fallow, cultivated fallow, and shaftal- and wheat-

Hibernation of stem borers in rice stubble in 4 fields in Muridkey and Narang, Pakistan.^a

Field	Larvae (no.)					Stubble infestation (%)	Moth emergence (%)
	Alive	Dead	Av/stubble	<i>Scirpophaga</i> sp.	<i>Sesamia</i> sp.		
<i>Muridkey</i>							
Shaftal sown	76.3	3.8	3.2	76.0	0.5	87.0	76.0
Wheat sown	22.3	16.2	1.5	21.0	1.3	39.7	52.1
Plowed fallow	16.0	24.1	1.6	15.5	0.5	24.7	30.5
Unplowed fallow	102.0	1.2	4.1	100.1	1.1	92.0	83.2
<i>Narang</i>							
Shaftal sown	121.2	3.8	4.9	120.4	0.8	93.5	78.2
Wheat sown	34.5	17.1	1.7	33.4	0.9	40.2	47.7
Plowed fallow	17.8	27.4	1.8	17.0	0.8	24.0	22.0
Unplowed fallow	146.4	4.0	6.1	140.1	1.3	98.0	87.0

^aAv of 2 years data.

sown fields. One hundred stubble were collected from each of 5-7 sites at Muridkey and Narang in Dec-Jan 1981-82 and 1982-83. A subsample of 25 stubble from each collection was dissected. Number of live and dead larvae, larval species, larvae per stubble, and percent infestation were recorded. Another subsample of 25

stubble was placed in dark cages with moisture and temperature similar to those in fields. Killing bottles were attached to an exit-to-light where the emerging moths were trapped and counted (see table).

The studies indicate that destroying rice stubble after harvest is essential to minimizing SB incidence. □

Effect of azolla on insect predators

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Azolla floats on paddy water and creates in the rice field ecosystem an additional niche that influences insect predators living on or in the water. Net samples including applied and naturally occurring azolla, paddy water, and bottom mud were taken 12 times from Oct to Dec 1982 from transplanted rice fields on the IRRI experimental farm. More predators were counted in samples taken from fields with applied azolla (303) than from other fields (191) (see table).

The water-surface inhabiting species most favored by azolla were rice hopper predators *Microvelia douglasi atrolineata*

Effect of azolla on rice insect predator populations in a rice field, IRRI farm, 6 Oct to 16 Dec 1982.

	Predators (no./family) ^a																	Total		
	Hemiptera								Coleoptera				Odonata		Araneae					
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q		R	S
With azolla	57	38	28	26	4	2	2	1	24	18	14	11	8	6	170	42	2	1	2	303
Without azolla	31	20	16	10	3	2	13.2		18	20	9	10	4	6	27	16	1	0	1	191

^aTotal of 12 net samples. A = Veliidae, B = Pleidae, C = Notonectidae, D = Mesoveliidae, E = Ochtereidae, F = Nepidae, G = Gerridae, H = Belostomatidae, I = Dytiscidae, J = Hydrophilidae, K = Hydracarinae, L = Gyrinidae, M = Carabidae, N = Staphylinidae, O = Coenagrionidae, P = Libellulidae, Q = Lycosidae, R = Theridiosomatidae, S = Theridiidae, and T = Tetragnathidae.

(Bergroth) [Veliidae], *Paraplea sobrina* (Stål) [Pleidae], and *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Boes. et Str.) [Lycosidae]. The rice bund-inhabiting spiders *Pardosa birmanica* Simon, *Arctosa janetscheki* Buchar, and *Hippasa rimandoi* Baxion [Lycosidae] moved into the azolla. Among the subsurface species, azolla favored noto-

nectid backswimmers, pleid water bugs, water treaders, and coenagrionid damselfly naiads.

Surface-dwelling gerrid water striders and the libellulid dragonfly preferred open water. Other groups of insect predators either were unaffected by azolla or were too few to allow comparisons. □

Pathogens and nematodes for control of rice water weevil in Cuba

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Rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus brevisos-tris* (Suffr.) has few natural enemies in Cuba. We conducted laboratory and field

studies to identify fungi, bacteria, and nematodes with potential to control rice water weevil.

Various strains of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarrhizium anisopliae* fungi were tested in the laboratory. Because rice water weevils live below the water surface, fungi cannot be applied directly to adults. Some fungi were broadcast on the water surface in the laboratory and in-

fectured insects when they surfaced. When adult rice water weevils were contaminated with *B. bassiana* strain 32, mortality was 95% at 20 days (Table 1) and 100% at 32 days after infection. When 2 kg *B. bassiana* 32 was broadcast on a 2-ha rice field adult mortality was 88% 15 days after application.

None of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* bio-preparations (Bitoxibacilin, Insectin, Den-